

STUDIES ON THE FRIES MIGRATION. PART I

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The Fries migration has been carried out in the case of six esters of *cyclohexanepropionic acid* with a view to studying the effect of *cyclohexane* ring on the rearrangement and to studying the amoebicidal activity of the hydroxyketones.

It was observed by Fries and Fink (*Ber.*, 1908, 41, 4271) that acyl derivatives of phenols, when heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride, were converted smoothly into the isomeric *ortho*- or *para*-hydroxyketones, or into a mixture of the two.

Considerable amount of work has been carried out in this field with esters of unsaturated aliphatic carboxylic acids (Sen and Misra, this *Journal*, 1948, 28, 393; 1949, 26, 149) and saturated aliphatic carboxylic acids, as well as with aromatic carboxylic acids (cf. Adams, "Organic Reaction", Vol. 1, pp. 357-363), but not with esters of alicyclic carboxylic acids.

We have therefore extended the reaction to esters of *cyclohexanepropionic acids*.

Six esters of *cyclohexanepropionic acid* with phenol, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-cresols, *p*-chloro- and *p*-bromo-phenols have been prepared.

The *ortho*- and *para*-hydroxyketones have been characterised through their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

EXPERIMENTAL

Phenyl Ester of cycloHexanepropionic Acid.—Phenol (5 g.) was dissolved in anhydrous benzene (25 c.c.), and well-cleaned and dried magnesium ribbon (1.0 g.) was put in it, followed by *cyclohexanepropionyl chloride* (10.0 g.), and the mixture was heated on a water-bath for 4 hours. The benzene was distilled off, and the ester taken in ether, washed with 1% NaOH solution and finally with water. After dehydration over anhydrous calcium chloride and distillation off of the ether, the ester was distilled under reduced pressure, b.p. 165°/3 mm, yield 10.2 g. (Found: C, 77.47; H, 8.56. $C_{15}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 77.58; H, 8.62%).

The following esters were prepared as above:

o-Cresyl Ester of cycloHexanepropionic Acid.—From the acid chloride (7.0 g.) and *o*-cresol (5.0 g.); yield 11.6 g., b.p. 205°/5 mm. (Found: C, 78.00; H, 8.90. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04; H, 8.94%).

m-Cresyl Ester of cycloHexanepropionic Acid.—From the acid chloride (7.0 g.) and *m*-cresol (5.0 g.); yield 10.6 g., b.p. 202°/11mm. (Found: C, 77.56; H, 8.80. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04; H, 8.94%).

p-Cresyl Ester of cycloHexanepropionic Acid.—From the acid chloride (8.0 g.) and *p*-cresol (5.0 g.), as white leaflets from ether, m.p. 72°; yield 9.5 g. (Found: C, 77.80; H, 8.92. $C_{16}H_{22}O_2$ requires C, 78.04; H, 8.94%).

p-Chlorophenyl Ester of cycloHexanepropionic Acid.—From the acid chloride (11.0 g.) and *p*-chlorophenol (6.0 g.), as shining crystals with ether, m.p. 63°, yield 11.9 g. (Found: C, 67.47; H, 7.09. $C_{15}H_{10}O_2Cl$ requires C, 67.54; H, 7.13%).

p-Bromophenyl Ester of cycloHexanepropionic Acid.—From the acid chloride (9.2 g.) and *p*-bromophenol (10.0 g.), as shining crystals with ether, m.p. 70°, yield 17.0 g. (Found: C, 57.68; H, 6.11. $C_{15}H_{10}O_2Br$, requires C, 57.80; H, 6.11%).

The Fries Rearrangement.—Finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (1.5 M), was added to the ester (1.0 M), dissolved in 15 c.c. of anhydrous carbon disulphide, and the mixture was heated on a steam-bath for 2 hours. Subsequently carbon disulphide was distilled off and the viscous mass was heated in an oil-bath at 120° for 2 hours. The oil separating was taken in ether, washed with sodium carbonate (1%), and finally with water. After dehydration over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether was distilled off and the liquid was distilled under vacuum.

Ortho and *para*-isomers of the ketones, obtained from the rearrangement of esters of *ortho*- and *meta*-cresols, were separated by steam-distillation.

The products which distilled with steam conformed to Pyma's test (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280) for *o*-hydroxyketones.

The ketones were converted into their 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazones (Table I).

TABLE I

Ester of cyclo- hexane- propionic acid with:	Ketone formed.	K e t o n e s.								2:4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones.	
		Yield.	B.P.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.		M.P.	Formula.	% Nitrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.			Found.	Calc.
Phenol	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy	13%	...	77.59	77.59	8.58	8.62	145°	$C_{21}H_{24}O_5N_4$	13.54	13.59
	<i>p</i> - "	51	210°/8 mm	77.53	77.59	8.60	8.62	155°	"	13.55	13.59
<i>o</i> -Cresol	<i>p</i> - "	50	157°/6	77.99	78.05	8.94	8.62	220°	$C_{23}H_{26}O_5N_4$	12.93	13.14
<i>m</i> -Cresol	<i>p</i> - "	44	200°/5	78.00	78.05	8.88	8.95	177°	"	13.09	13.14
<i>p</i> -Cresol	<i>o</i> - "	75	180°/2	77.85	78.05	8.44	8.95	170°	"	12.98	13.14
<i>p</i> -Chloro- phenol	<i>o</i> - "	80	196°/2	67.50	67.54	7.79	7.13	180°	$C_{21}H_{23}O_5N_4Cl$	12.40	12.54
<i>p</i> -Bromo- phenol	<i>o</i> - "	70	180°/5	57.80	57.80	5.09	6.11	152°	$C_{21}H_{23}O_5N_4Br$	11.19	11.40

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